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Department of Psychology
Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak, Haryana.

Associate Editors

Dr. Deepti Hooda

Professor of Psychology
Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak, Haryana.

Dr. Nilesh Thakre

Head Department of Psychology
SNDT Women's University,
Mumbai, Maharashtra.

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EDITORIAL

This issue of the *Journal of Indian Health Psychology* has presented nine research articles that focus on biopsychosocial aspects of health and illness with traditional empirical or qualitative and critically oriented approaches. The first article by Sonika and Deepti Hooda explored the role of emotional regulation in eating behaviour. They observed that difficulties in regulating emotions and poor emotion regulation strategies significantly account for disturbed and unhealthy eating behaviours. Manvi Singh, in the 2nd article, has taken up a sensitive issue of the predicament of the working woman which is increasingly attracting the attention of academicians and researchers. In the 3rd article Sajal Dhillon has explored the role of media on body image disturbance and eating disorders. The 4th article by Shamala.R and Madhurini Vallikad applied Protection Motivation Theory for effectively managing Covid-19 risk and suggested that two cognitive mediating processes, threat appraisal and coping appraisal, are the prerequisites for preventive behaviour and preparedness for pandemics. In the 5th article, Kalpna, Deepti Hooda and NovRattan Sharma empirically explored the role of self-control, aggression and cognitive distortion in criminal behavior. The 6th article by Gulgoona Jamal highlighted the effect of visual arts and performing arts in improving the psychological well-being of Indian young adult female amateur artists during COVID-19. Mandeep Sharma, Muni Ram and Sonu Kumar, in the 7th article, reported gender differences in adjustment, self-efficacy and academic achievement among school students. The findings of the 8th article by Pooja and Deepti Hooda point out significant the contribution of environmental attitude in predicting pro-environmental behavior. The last article of Sonika Dangi and Pankaj Gupta assessed the relationship between marital adjustment and depression amongst women.

The journal attempts to provide a platform for empirical research, comprehensive critical reviews and intervention-oriented articles in the field of health psychology and for application in a wide range of contexts. Editors express their gratitude to all the authors for their research contributions. Editors are also grateful to the referees and members of the editorial board for their valuable inputs and suggestions. The journal aims to sensitize the readers to various health-related biopsychosocial issues that would pave the path towards healthy and flourishing communities.

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CONTRIBUTION OF MEDIA ON BODY IMAGE DISTURBANCE AND EATING DISORDERS

*Sajal Dhillon**

Abstract

Survival of the human species depends on the consumption of healthy food which leads to a healthy mind and eventually to a healthy body. However, distortion may occur when an individual engages in hazardously abnormal food intake patterns and related thoughts and emotions. Standard medical manuals of 11th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) and Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5) identifies such behavioural engagements as eating disorders. Numerous types of eating disorders including- anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge eating disorder, pica, rumination disorder, avoidant/restrictive food intake disorder, and other specified feeding or eating disorder have been identified. Eating disorders impact the lives of millions of people irrespective of age, gender, and ethnicity upon being exposed to contributing factors of this mental disorder. The definite causal factors leading to the development of aforementioned eating disorders are unestablished- however, various researches have recognised the contribution of media in setting forth body image disturbances which ultimately leads to eating disorders. This present paper reviews the numerous researches for systematically analysing the contribution of media platforms on body dissatisfaction and eating disorders.

Keywords: Eating Disorder, Body Dissatisfaction, Media, Anorexia nervosa, Bulimia nervosa, Binge eating disorder, Pica, Rumination disorder, Avoidant/restrictive food intake disorder, Other Specified Feeding or Eating Disorder, ICD-11, DSM 5, mental disorder.

The act of consuming food is a basic necessity for human survival. Each one of us requires a balanced diet (full of essential carbohydrates, proteins, fat,

* Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology, Hisar, Haryana- 125001, India. Email: dhillonsajal910@gmail.com
Phone Number: 9729733910

vitamins, minerals and water) for physical as well as mental well-being. However, there exists complex behavioural conditions which are characterised by abnormal eating patterns and related thoughts and emotions. Such mental disorders are termed as “eating disorders”.

The 11th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) describes feeding or eating disorders under block L1-6B8 as disorders involving “abnormal eating or feeding behaviours that are not explained by another health condition and are not developmentally appropriate or culturally sanctioned.” ICD-11 further elaborates that feeding or eating disorders are inclusive of such disturbances in behavioural patterns that are unrelated to weight and shape of the body like consuming inedible substances or purposeful regurgitating food.

American Psychological Association (APA) termed eating disorders as “any disorder characterized primarily by a pathological disturbance of attitudes and behaviors related to food”.

The standard medical manuals- 11th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) and Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)- classifies the eating disorders as: Anorexia nervosa (AN), Bulimia nervosa (BN), Binge eating disorder (BED), Pica, Rumination disorder, Avoidant/restrictive food intake disorder (ARFID), and Other Specified Feeding or Eating Disorder (OSFED).

The causal factors leading to the development of these aforementioned eating disorders are unestablished- however, innumerable researches have recognised the contribution of media in setting forth body image disturbances which ultimately leads to eating disorders.

Role of Media

Living in the digital age, all of us bear witness to the ever-growing impact of media in our daily lives. Be it the television, fashion magazines, or social media, all of them portray unrealistic and unachievable ideas. Such portrayals kick in body dissatisfaction, one of the most consistent risk factors of eating disorders, in the general population especially the younger generations.

Media Exposure of Females to Body Dissatisfaction and Eating Disorders

Major chunk of research work concerning the influence of media on eating disorders has been centred around females. All formats of mass media have been notorious for featuring unnaturally slimmed models who have further been exposed to extensive photoshopping.

Hamilton and Waller (1993) conducted an experimental study for looking into the influence of media on estimation of body size in women having anorexia nervosa or bulimia nervosa. The sample size was 24. The findings of the study suggested that when exposed to photographs of models circulated in fashion magazines only for 6-7 minutes, there was a 25% increase in the overestimation of body size by bulimic and anorexic women.

Stice et al. (1994) investigated the exposure of media, thin women idealisation and its everlasting impact upon development of eating disorders. A total of 238 female students in their undergraduate programs were taken up as participants. The structural natured equation of modelling reported to be having a direct influence of exposure to media upon eating disorders.

In the year 1997, Garner published a survey, in *Psychology Today*, in which he established the significant promotion of cultural beauty and body thinness ideals via mass media. The sample pool was 3453 women. 23% of whom reflected on being influenced by the bodies of television celebrities. Furthermore, 89% of the women wanted to lose weight. Correlation between body weight and body dissatisfaction was also established- heavy weighted women were more dissatisfied. It was also revealed that about 50% of the women smoked cigarettes for weight control.

Field et al. (1999) conducted a cross-sectional survey with the aim of assessing the influence of media upon weight loss behaviours and body shape and body weight perceptions of 548 grade 5 to grade 12 female students. 69% girls through the survey reported being influenced by fashion magazines in defining their perfect body images and 47% wanted to lose weight due to the same. Positive association was further found between frequency of following fashion magazines and prevalence of engaging in abnormal dieting behaviours to achieve bodies similar to that of underweight models.

In a research from White et al. (2015) the contribution of media exposure to eating disorder behavioural attitudes in women having anorexia nervosa was examined. The sample size was 118 women with anorexia nervosa. It was found that media exposure (specifically the stress which was caused by media exposure) increased the tendency of increment in liquid diet and restriction in intake of solid food items, voluntarily vomiting, and abuse of laxatives in women with anorexia nervosa.

Naumann et al. (2016) undertook a study with the aim of testing the impact of emotional regulation strategies of rumination and acceptance on media regulated body dissatisfaction of individuals with eating disorders. 78 women (Anorexia Nervosa=39 and Bulimia Nervosa=39) were made to watch model images and were further made to use emotional regulation strategies (acceptance and rumination). The results of the study showed that the technique of acceptance significantly improved media induced body dissatisfaction in bulimia nervosa cases. Rumination was found to be significantly helpful with body dissatisfaction caused by media in both, anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. These results were independent of changes in the mood of women with anorexia and bulimia.

Barney et al. (2022) undertook a report of clinical observation of a 9 year old with Rumination disorder, Avoidant/restrictive food intake disorder (ARFID). The 9 year old was severely malnourished and placed extreme importance upon body thinness. It was reported by the patient that such positive value upon thinness was placed due to beauty ideals of social media as well as glorification of petite bodies by the society. This ultimately led her to engage in disordered eating patterns.

Leverage of Media Exposure on Male Population

As most of the research work has been directed towards the impact of mass media exposure upon female adolescents, its influence on males in their adolescent years also needs exploration- the uneasiness of the body, issues related to body image, eating disorders, etc.

Dakanalis et al. (2015) engaged into a three year longitudinal study for exploring the developmental impact of media driven body idealisation, objectification of the self amongst adolescents, abnormal dieting behaviours and engagement in binge eating. Data was collected from 685 adolescents. The results of the study revealed that the adolescents engaged in scrutinising their bodies and self-objectification when they were exposed to media idealisation of bodies. The adolescents thus experienced negative emotions which ultimately converted into restricted eating and binge eating behavioural patterns. Gender differences in these associations were not observed.

Barcaccia et al. (2017) also conducted a study in this direction upon the potential influence of models broadcasted by television upon young Italian boys and girls. The sample size was 301 adolescents in the age range of 14 to 19 years. Contributing factors for eating disordered activities amongst females were identified to be their personal wishes to look like television portrayed characters, consumption of reality based entertainment programmes, and cognitive dissonance in real and idealistic bodies. Males as well as females were most influenced by the desires of their friends to look like television characters and this contributed the most to cases of body uneasiness, anxiety, depression, and ultimately eating disorders.

Sharma et al. (2019) further undertook a cross-sectional study to investigate the role of media in shaping perceptions of body image and abnormal eating behaviours amongst Indian medical undergraduate students. The sample of 370 undergraduate students of the medical field aged 17 to 30 years were selected using stratified random sampling. The results of the study showcased that around 35.4% students had abnormal perceptions concerning body image. 21.1% reported abnormal eating behaviours. 42.2% of the students admitted to regard media as the primary source of knowing the attractiveness standards. 27.6% felt the pressure to be attractive. 36.5% agreed to be influenced by models and 40.5% by athletic figures. Overall, it was found that male students were more likely than female students to be engaged in abnormal eating attitudes and being pressured by the media for achieving idealistic bodies.

Cultural Perspective

Cultural dynamics also play their specific role in shaping societal norms as well as social inequality. To verify this, Abigail and Gruys (2010) drew upon a case study where comparisons were done on American eating disorders' and obesity's news reporting between the years 1995 and 2005. The flag-bearer of western world- United States of America associates thinness of body with moral virtuousness and significantly higher social status. Fat bodies were viewed with inferiority and signs were linked with gluttony and sloth. The original set of data also associated complex factors with anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. Overweight was treated by the media as a lifestyle choice and binge eating was blamed on poor self-control. The stereotype of poor and minorities being overweight, lazy and out of control was fed by the media outlets. The bigger bodies of African-American women was viewed as a protest towards thinness-related eating disorders.

With the introduction of western media, multiple "media naïve populations" of the world have also been exposed to the dangers of body dissatisfaction. One such population is Fijian school going girls. Becker et al. (2002) conducted a study upon 63 school girls who consume prolonged hours of western television shows. The girls showed significantly higher levels of interest in engaging in unhealthy and abnormal procedures to lose weight and model themselves into the characters broadcasted by the television. Decades later, exposure to unrealistic body images still lead to body dissatisfaction and ultimately eating disorders amongst the adolescent females is still prevalent. Laohapongphan et al. (2016) also undertook a study in the Asian country of Thailand with the aim of investigating the causal relationship between mass media exposure to thin idleness and eating disorders. For this current study, a sample of 1064 female students in their undergraduate programs from Bangkok were taken. The age range was 18-23. The results of the study confirmed a direct as well as indirect relationship between the impact of mass media, the influence of mass media on eating

disorders and the self esteem of the individual. Media's footprints are also clearly visible in the lives of rural, least-developed world's female adolescents. With the objective of examining the prevalence of body dissatisfaction and eating disorders upon media exposure (internet, television, magazines and radio), Terhoeven et al. (2020) conducted a study amongst rural female adolescents of north-western Burkina Faso. The sample size was 696 adolescents in the age range of 12 to 20. The results showed that 16% of the participants' Body Mass Index (BMI) was below the WHO standard while that of 4% was above it. Historically eating disorders are rare in the rural set-up of Burkina Faso. However, with the increment in exposure to social media, body dissatisfaction and ultimately the prevalence of eating disorders are on the potential rise.

Advent of Social media and Eating Disorders

With the genesis of social media, the world has been provided with an interactive, internet-based platform where individuals can share their ideas, images and can also communicate with one another. However, like all great inventions of the world, social-media also comes with its downfalls.

Social media attitudes associated with physical appearance have been viewed as risk factors indicating eating disorders. Lonergan et al. (2020) conducted a study with the aim of looking into the linkage of excessive social media's appearance related behaviours and greater odds of meeting the diagnostic criteria for eating disorders. The sample size for this study was 4209 Australian adolescents (53.15% females). The consequence of avoiding posting edited photographs and selfies was examined. Higher levels of avoidance were linked with greater odds of fulfilling the eating disorder diagnostic criteria with the exception of purging disorder and binge eating disorder. All the probability of eating disorders' diagnosis was met when the participants engaged in heightened photograph investment. Quite similar association was evident for manipulation of photographs, except for unspecified feeding and eating disorder, and binge-eating disorder. Involvement with the selfies of others was found to be related to all the eating disorders with the criterion exception of purging disorder and anorexia nervosa. A significant role of gender was also evident whereby males were more inclined to be diagnosed with anorexia nervosa in relation to higher selfie posting avoidance.

Turner & Lefevre (2017) shed light upon the impact of social media influencer culture where hundreds of thousand people follow the lead of their favourite online celebrities into consuming food in an abnormal pattern which has underlying clinical implications of development of eating disorders. Turner & Lefevre conducted an online survey to investigate the link between social media usage, in particularity Instagram, and symptoms of orthorexia nervosa. Orthorexia nervosa is an eating disorder in which the individual is obsessed with consumption of

healthy food. Orthorexia nervosa often exists co-morbidly with anorexia nervosa. The sample size was 680. Through the results, it was seen that with higher usage of Instagram there was a significantly greater tendency (49%) than the general population (less than 1%) towards orthorexia nervosa.

Wiesmann (2022) conducted a cross-sectional study which aimed at investigating the influence of using social networking sites in mediating the relation between orthorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa amongst university students. The sample size was 242. Through the results, a positive correlation was established between orthorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. Thus, bulimia nervosa being a determinant factor for developing orthorexia. Further, a negative correlation was also seen between time spent on social networking sites and orthorexia nervosa—the consumption of social networking sites reduced the symptoms of orthorexia nervosa. Ultimately, Wiesmann (2022) concluded that there exists a partial mediation in the relation between bulimia nervosa and orthorexia nervosa. This mediation might be inconsistent.

Time and again the relationship between usage of the internet and development of eating disorders amongst young adults have been established. The underlying mechanisms often get brushed away and aren't ever clarified. Imperatori et al. (2021) tested the hypothesis that excessive broadcasting of ideally toned and thinned bodily images over social media platforms causes body dissatisfaction, and ultimately triggers eating disorders. For this present study, a total of 721 young adults in the age range of 18 to 34 years were selected. The results of the study put forward that the ultimate effect of social media addiction were significantly related to eating disorders related symptoms. This association was also significantly mediated by muscle dysmorphia symptoms.

In contrast to the aversive effect of social media particularly Instagram in promoting body dissatisfaction, online communities also offer support to individuals facing eating disorders and are unable to take help from professionals. Au & Cosh (2022) conducted a mixed-method survey study where 163 individuals relied upon Instagram communities for recovery assistance. Diverse ethnics groups suffering from potential cases of binge eating disorders, anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa are confronted by such recovery groups. Results of the survey indicated that such recovery communities are significantly beneficiary in providing social validation and social support. However there should be a moderate level of usage of such support groups because over-reliance may lead to exposure to detrimental content, ultimately preventing the necessary recovery. Promotion of better professional treatment accessibility is a dire need.

Cognizance of Media's Harmful Influence

Mostly it has been evident with years of research that unawareness and discomfort with one's own skin leads to vulnerability mainly amongst adolescent

girls to adapt extreme eating behaviours. However, the study conducted by Tiggemann et al. (2000) showed a newer perspective. This study was administered upon 67 school girls where the obvious significant negative impact of excessive media consumption results in pressures of becoming thin. Thus, forcing them to adapt disordered patterns of eating. The more interesting part of the findings was the presence of awareness regarding the hazardous role media places in promoting idealistic bodies. In spite of their keen interest in becoming slimmer, they did not display any dissatisfaction with their own bodies.

Conclusion

Although the world became a global village with the origination of mass media, it also witnessed its darker side. Countless individuals of all ages, especially younger generations, gender, and ethnicity have been exposed to hours of prolonged media usage in one format or the other. Consequently, they have been predisposed to idealise the people and their unrealistically photoshopped thin and toned bodies whom they see on the fashion magazines, television, or/and social media platforms. Numerous researches have highlighted that such experiences from a very young age leads to body dissatisfaction setting in which is often followed by abnormal eating behaviour patterns and clinically diagnosed eating disorders. In the current times it is, therefore, the need of the hour to spread adequate awareness as well as provide professional help to the individuals in need.

Further research

Further research is needed to identify the appropriate educational intervention as well as the preventive interventions at the academies level. Identification of active components of such intervention is also required for the promotion of healthy body imagery and appropriate eating behaviour patterns.

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